

Public Speech in the Culture of Livonia: A Political and Social Phenomenon in the European Performative Tradition (1200-1600) (No. Izp-2024/1-0296)

Version 2

Description

The object of project Public Speech in the Culture of Livonia: A Political and Social Phenomenon in the European Performative Tradition (1200-1600) (Izp-2024/1-0296) is public speech in Livonia in the context of medieval European performative culture. The research group will focus on public speech as a phenomenon of political and social communication in medieval Livonian urban communities. The research will reveal that public speech was a frequently used medium and tool of social/political influence in the public communication and ritual practices of different social groups – civic elites and non-elites, clergy and monastic communities, artisan brotherhoods and guilds – through which community identities were established, stabilised or deconstructed. The research material of the project team will be documentary and epistolary texts, chronicles and other groups of written sources; the content of these texts, produced in the 13th-16th centuries both in Livonia and in European intellectual centres and shaped by the rhetorical traditions of biblical, classical and humanist thought, reveals the presence of public speech. The analytical study of public speech as a cultural experience and tradition has not been systematically carried out in either Livonian or Northern European historical societies and is therefore considered innovative.

The contribution of this project to Latvian society is new knowledge that will stimulate interest in important issues of Baltic and European history in the early modern period. The knowledge that public speech in Livonian historical communities was an indispensable tool for their cohesion and decision-making will highlight the importance of public communication and its historical tradition in the Baltic Sea region in contemporary Latvian public discourses. The acquisition of such knowledge will provide representatives of

Latvian society from all walks of life with a deeper understanding of their belonging to the Western European cultural tradition and its democratic decision-making practices.

Funder

LCS

Grant

Public Speech in the Culture of Livonia: A Political and Social Phenomenon in the European Performative Tradition (1200-1600) (No. Izp-2024/1-0296)

Researchers

Gustavs Strenga (0000-0002-9175-4785), Rudolfs Reinis Vitolins (0009-0004-0086-1086), Andris Levans (0000-0003-4676-4703)

Organizations

Latvian Academy of Culture, University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Public Speech in the Culture of Livonia: A Political and Social Phenomenon in the European Performative Tradition \(1200-1600\) \(No. Izp-2024/1-0296\)](#)

Description:

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Organizations:

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Contact: Vitolins Rudolfs Reinis (rudolfs_reinis.vitolins@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: LCS

Grants: Public Speech in the Culture of Livonia: A Political and Social Phenomenon in the European Performative Tradition (1200-1600) (No. Izp-2024/1-0296)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Public Speech in Livonian documents

Representations in Livonian documents with public speech aimed at social group in crisis or changing.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Cases of public speech mentioned or constructed in document sources (statutes and normative texts of guilds and brotherhoods, and materials of the Landtag (Diets) meetings such as their protocols)

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

TB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The research community - regional, local and global. Researchers and students in the social sciences and humanities, the general public, mainly in Latvia (partly also in the Baltic States), policy makers who themselves use public speech as a means of communication in their daily lives.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Aim of document

Aim of author of the document

Social/ political aim of episode in document

Communication type (oath, speech) in document

Aim of speakers

signal words (oratio , orat, dicit, ait, sprake, rede, spreket, spoken, gesprochen)

Context of speech act

Speaker/-s (title, occupation)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Till the end of project (01.01.2028)

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall

- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Public Speech in chronicles of Livonia

Public speech representations in Livonian chronicles aimed to a group in a situation of crisis or change.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Purpose is to identify the presence of public speech in Livonian chronicles and it's aim.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Machine-readable text
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

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1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

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1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

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Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Aim of chronicle

Aim of chronicler Social/ political aim of episode in text

Communication type (oath, speech) in episode

Aim of speakers

signal words (oratio , orat, dicit, ait, sprake, rede, spreket, spoken, gesprochen)

Context of speech act

Speaker/-s

Type of speech

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zenodo.org

<https://zenodo.org/>

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